

A QUARTER OF A CENTURY, IN THE SERVICE OF MOUNTAIN COMMUNITIES IN ROMANIA. THE COURSE OF THE SPECIALIZED STRUCTURE FOR THE MOUNTAIN AREA IN VATRA DORNEI, FROM A TRAINING CENTER FOR ADULTS, TO A GOVERNMENT AGENCY. NEW MAJOR CHALLENGES IN THE CURRENT NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN CONTEXT

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Abstract

Until 1989, there was no specific legal framework for the mountain area, through which the specificity of the mountain could be the subject of a differentiated mountain policy. Nor specialized public institutions for mountain development. After 1990, a number of institutions and bodies with a role in the field were created. By Government Decision no. 888 of December 9, 1994, the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC - was established as a public institution with legal personality, subordinated to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food, based in Vatra Dornei, Suceava County, in the "Motel Runc" building, Runc Street - no number. Between July 2003 and April 2004, CEFIDEC was taken over by the National Agency for Agricultural Consulting Bucharest, and will regain its legal personality in May 2004. From December 2009, the institution becomes a component part of the National Agency for Mountain Areas - ANZM (based in Alba Iulia). In September 2010, the National Agency of Mountain Areas was abolished, CEFIDEC being implicitly abolished as well. Between September 2010 and August 2015, within the structure from Vatra Dornei, a service of the General Directorate for Rural Development - Management Authority for PNDR from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development functioned. In December 2014, the Mountain Area Agency will be re-established, which will also have as its directorate the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians. And, in December 2018, by GD no. 1036/2018, the Mountain Area Agency changes its title, becoming the National Mountain Area Agency, keeping CEFIDEC, as a direction within the agency. The major present and future new challenges of the institution, aim at the elaboration of the National Strategy for sustainable development of the mountain area, of the National Strategic Plan (chapter related to the mountain area), of some projects and department development programs for the mountain inhabitants of Romania.

***Keywords:** CEFIDEC, ANCA, DGDR-AMPNDR, AZM, ANZM, mountain area, professional training, consultancy, policies, strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the socio-economic development of the mountain area in Romania has been achieved depending on the existing political systems and the way in which governments are involved.

During the socialist period, there was no official delimitation of the mountain area. Also, this area did not benefit from distinct legislation, specific education, specialized institutions or differentiated politics. The economy of mountain areas was limited to the extractive industry, the food industry, forestry, services, raising animals and land cultivation, especially for family needs. Farmers in the mountain area did not have the professional training acquired through school, to carry out agricultural activities, these being usually carried out, according to the experiences passed down from generation to generation. The only information

about this sector was taught in rural schools, in the gymnasium, at the Agriculture and Knowledge about nature classes.

In the 1980s, there were several local or regional initiatives to enhance mountain agricultural resources. Through some less inspired it was tried an association between mountain farmers and creation of state farms. But there have been also successful initiatives. One of them was represented by the "Mountain University" based in Vatra Dornei - founded by Dr. vet. Radu Rey and Eng. Agr. Mihai Vleju - entity that brought together teachers from universities in Bucharest, Cluj and Iasi, animal breeders, shepherds and veterinarians from Vatra Dornei villages. This organization was concerned with the study of the history of civilization in the area of Dorna Country and participated in the amplification and improvement of socio-economic life in all mountainous localities of the country [16].

In 1994, Prof. Dr. Radu Rey, Director General of the National Agency for Mountain Areas, developed the project and determined the creation of the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians. A public institution, subordinated to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food, whose main tasks were to fill the gaps in knowledge of the mountain economy, correcting - on a scientific basis - errors in practice, a good orientation of farmers, agricultural specialists and other categories of factors responsible for the sustainable development of the mountain countryside. Also, the new institution aimed to contribute to the dissemination of knowledge on the specific elements of agriculture and rural-mountain economy and the environment, identifying opportunities for development of local resources and the formation of a general mountain culture in Romania.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was carried out by consulting the archives and databases of the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC Vatra Dornei, National Agency for Agricultural Consulting, General Management for Rural Development AM PNDR, Mountain Area Agency and National Agency for Mountain Areas, of some documents elaborated by representative associations, of the school textbooks elaborated before 1989, of the reports drawn up by the trainees / students who carried out internships at the structures of the mountain area between 1996 - 2020. At the same time, were consulted specialized literature, profile sites and were watched films from the socialist period, posted online. As methods of data collection and analysis, the following were used: interview, observation, document analysis. The aim was to collect, synthesize and process data from different sources, transpose and adapt existing studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After 1990, in the new political and economical situation, several initiatives were launched to support the mountain areas and their inhabitants, starting from the idea that until then there were no specialized institutions and no agro-mountain education for this area. Thus, by Government Decision no. 888 of December 9, 1994, the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC (fig.2) - was established as a public institution with legal personality, subordinated to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food, based in Vatra Dornei, Suceava County, in the former "Motel Runc" (fig.1), from Runc Street - without number [7].

Among the main objects of activity of CEFIDEC were the following: training of specialists in the fields of mountain agriculture, civil servants who provide training and advice

to mountain farmers in the field of economy and specific mountain habitat, the activity of introducing technical, economical and social progress; professional training and information of the farmers, dissemination of knowledge about the mountain area and protection of the mountain environment, contributing to the formation of a mountain culture in Romania, participation in the development of innovative projects and programs on economic and social development in the mountain area; elaboration of framework projects and pilot projects meant for the development of mountain peasant households and provision of consultancy and technical assistance for farmers, economic agents and institutions for the elaboration of development projects in the mountain countryside; collaboration with specialized institutions in the field of scientific research for the development of the mountain rural economy.

Fig. 1. Students and lecturers in front of the building for the mountain area of Vatra Dornei:
Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC

Since 1995, within this center, unique in Romania, specialists have been hired, through competition, for the following fields: sociology, agronomy, horticulture, economics, zooculture, veterinary medicine, construction, tourism, forestry, to which were added later, agricultural mechanics, food industry, computer science, architecture. In order to become trainers - consulting experts on fields of activity specific to the mountain area, the specialists followed a specific training course, carried out by the Center for Staff Training in Private Agriculture Bucharest - Băneasa [1].

Fig. 2. Logos for the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC (initial and final)

Fig. 3. Inauguration of the CEFIDEC headquarters. Sanctification service

Between December 1994 and July 2003 the structure for the mountain area from Vatra Dornei - CEFIDEC functioned as an institution with legal personality, subordinated to the Ministry of Agriculture and Food / Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, Waters and Environment, under the coordination of the National Agency for Mountain Areas - ANZM (direction within the ministry).

The management of the institution was ensured by: eng. Vasile Ardelean, director in the period 1994 - 2000 and eng. Dănuț Gițan director 2000 - 2003. Coordinator of the training courses: prof. Dr. Radu Rey, general director of ANZM (1994 - 1997) / head of service mountain area within the Ministry of Agriculture (1997 - 2000) / ANZM director (2000 - 2002).

The main types of courses held at CEFIDEC Vatra Dornei from the establishment until 2003:

- 1). Improvement courses:

➤ « A » type courses: training of counselors for rural-mountain development - addressed to specialists from the management for agriculture and rural development from the 28 counties with mountain area in Romania (identified at that time), lasting 6 weeks, performed in three training stages, separated by time intervals for documentation and data collection in the field. Completion of the courses consists of supporting three sustainable development projects in the mountain area (specific areas such as: agriculture, small investments, agrotourism, etc.), preparation of socio-economic monograph of the locality where the student works and obtaining the certificate of "Counselor for rural development in the mountains".

➤ - Type « B » courses: With a duration of one week, intended for decision making or with responsibilities regarding rural development within the Ministry of Agriculture or within the General Management for Agriculture from the 28 counties with mountain areas in Romania or other interested institutions, at request.

➤ - Type « C » courses: short courses, on various topics of interest, organized on request, for farmers in the mountain area, institutions, organizations, associations or other entities with concerns in the development of the mountain area in Romania.

During the courses, the following fields were approached: the basics of rural-mountain development, agriculture, horticulture, zooculture - specifically mountain, agri-food technologies, architecture and rural constructions, basic notions on cadastre and property in the mountain area, forestry and environmental protection, rural sociology in the mountain area, elements of economy of the mountain peasant household, management for the rural countryside, rural tourism and mountain agro-tourism, culinary art and serving technique, initiation and administration of business in rural areas, English, primary use of computer.

Fig. 4. Initial team of Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians - CEFIDEC (February 1997)

Between July 2003 and April 2004, the team from CEFIDEC was taken over by the National Agency for Agricultural Consulting - ANCA (fig. 5), based in Bucharest; the specialists still carrying out their activity in the building from Vatra Dornei.

The management of the institution was provided by: eng. Greta Popa - ANCA and eng. Dănuț Gițan - CEFIDEC.

During that period, of 10 months, the professional training programs of type A, B and C continued.

Fig. 5. The logo of National Agency for Agricultural Consulting - ANCA

In 2004, CEFIDEC regained its legal personality, according to GD no. 739 of July 3, 2003 on the organization and functioning of the Ministry of Agriculture, Forests, Waters and Environment [8]. Type A, B and C courses were still organized. The institution operated with the same staff, taken over from ANCA.

In the 2001-2005 period, CEFIDEC Vatra Dornei carried out the Project "Training and extension for rural areas in Romania" [14], organized and financed by a financial assistance program of the World Bank, aimed to support agricultural services and implementation of a competitive grant scheme (SCG). Through this project, the aim was:

- training of trainers in the fields of mountain agriculture, of specialists who train and provide advice to mountain farmers
- professional training of farmers and knowledge extension regarding the mountain specifics and protection of the environment in the mountain area of Romania

Agricultural extension activities were carried out for farmers in the mountain area, by setting up 30 demonstration lots with potatoes, sown meadows, fodder crops, fruit bush plantations, vegetables, medicinal plants and by publishing brochures and leaflets on various topics of interest:

- Mountain forest ecosystems;
- Raising cattle in the mountain household;
- Agro-tourism in the mountain countryside;
- Food processing and hygiene technologies in the mountain household;
- Constructions in the mountain rural area;
- Ecological management of mountain meadows;

Other types of courses organized by CEFIDEC after 2004:

- Rural Diagnosis Courses and business planning in rural areas - lasting 4 days, addressed to specialists in the mountain area.

➤ Rural Construction Courses in the mountain area - lasting 4 days, for specialists from the Directorates for Agriculture and Rural Development (DADR) in the counties with mountain areas.

➤ Intensive English and computer courses - for specialists from the network of the Ministry of Agriculture, the Directorates for Agriculture and Rural Development and the County Agricultural Consulting Centers, carried out in one or two course modules - depending on the request - of 2 weeks each, concluded with Graduation exam.

➤ Courses organized on request, on different fields, lasting 2 or 5 days, at the institution's headquarters or in the mountain territory.

Courses organized in partnership with other institutions, within projects:

➤ Training of ANCA/ CEFIDEC experts to become service providers, oriented to the "farmers' needs", carried out in partnership with InWent Germany (2007).

➤ Initiation and orientation courses in agro-tourism and mountain rural development for groups of "actors" from the mountain area of Ukraine (border region with Suceava county): young farmers, agricultural specialists, mayors, school principals and district officials and regional - carried out within the project "Education for sustainable mountain rural development through agro-tourism - Kiss of the mountains", developed by the National Association for Rural Mountain Development Romontana / CEFIDEC, within the Neighborhood Program Romania - Ukraine 2004 - 2006, (2006 - 2008).

➤ Active tourism in the Dornelor Basin (2009) within the Agronatur Project "Transfer of innovative training itineraries to the rural environment".

➤ Practical course on wind energy "I can build it myself" (2010) in partnership with the SpeoBucovina Club Speleological Foundation, within the Project "Ecotourism in the Land of Thorns - a tool for sustainable development" - NorwayGrants Program.

➤ All types of courses conducted by CEFIDEC, contained both theoretical activities and a balanced program of practical activities, with field demonstrations, at different objectives, including pilot stations for rural development, conducted through PHARE and SAPARD programs, lots and demonstration farms built with the support of the World Bank.

2). Training courses:

Starting with 2005, CEFIDEC organized a series of qualification courses, which took place both at the institution's headquarters in Vatra Dornei and in the mountain territory of the neighboring counties [12]:

Level 1 qualification courses for the title "Agro-tourism worker", organized in accordance with the provisions of O.G. no. 129/2000, approved by Law no. 375/2002, regarding the education of adults, based on the authorization SV Nr. 33/28 04.04 2005.

The training program lasted 360 hours, of which 120 hours of theoretical training and 240 hours of practical training and was structured in order to acquire the skills provided by the Vocational Training Standard.

The qualification program was a real success; many of the participants in this program, being owners of agri-tourism structures, or entrepreneurs who were to start an activity in this regard.

Level 2 qualification courses for the title "Mountain farmer", organized in accordance with the provisions of O.G. no. 129/2000, approved by Law no. 375/2002, regarding the education of adults, based on the authorization SV Nr. 33/29 04.04 2005.

The training program lasted 720 hours, of which 240 hours of theoretical training and 480 hours of practical training and was structured in order to acquire the skills provided by the Vocational Training Standard.

Level 2 qualification courses for the “Mountain Farmer” occupation, organized in accordance with the provisions of O.G. no. 129/2000, approved by Law no. 375/2002, regarding the education of adults, based on the authorization of PS Nr. 33/20 04.04 2005.

The training program lasted 720 hours, of which 240 hours of theoretical training and 480 hours of practical training and was structured in order to acquire the skills provided by the Vocational Training Standard.

Level 2 qualification courses for the title “Tourist guesthouse administrator”, organized in accordance with the provisions of O.G. no. 129/2000, approved by Law no. 375/2002, regarding adult education, based on the authorization SV No. 33/19 06.02 2008.

The training program lasted 720 hours, of which 240 hours of theoretical training and 480 hours of practical training and was structured in order to acquire the skills provided by the Vocational Training Standard. In this course, the following areas were addressed: effective communication at work, multidisciplinary team work, computer information management, promoting the image of the guesthouse, organizing the activity within the tourist guesthouse, monitoring the application of NPM and NPSI, checking financial management, direct promotion of the tourist product, concluding contracts with customers, carrying out specific accommodation and food operations, ensuring a favorable climate for tourists, providing boarding services to the client, organizing optional tourist programs, providing information of tourist interest, resolving customer complaints.

The management of the institution was provided by: Dr. Eng. Dănuț Gițan (2004 - 2009) - director and Dr. Eng. Mioara Bocănici - Deputy Director (2007 - 2009).

In December 2009, the staff of the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians CEFIDEC Vatra Dornei was taken over (transferred in the interest of the service) by the National Agency for Mountain Areas (fig. 6), which in turn was moved from the Ministry of Agriculture (MADR) in Bucharest to Alba Iulia, Alba county, in accordance with Law 329/2009 (Art .64), on the reorganization of public authorities and institutions, rationalization of public expenditures, support for the business environment and compliance with framework agreements with the European Commission and the International Monetary Fund [11].

Fig. 6. Logo of National Agency of Mountain Area (existing in 2009)

The 29 employees of the center were taken over entirely by ANZM, and they continued to work in the building from Vatra Dornei; at the headquarters in Alba Iulia there was only a number of 4 specialists.

The following departments operated within the National Agency for Mountain Areas (ANZM):

- Laboratory of agronomy, zooculture and mountain forestry;

- Laboratory of socio-economy and mountain rural development;
- Laboratory of rural constructions, mechanization and renewable energies;
- Computer laboratory, modern languages, writing and editing publications;
- Financial, accounting, legal, human resources management office;
- Public information and relations with the press;
- Internal public audit;
- Administrative.

CEFIDEC continued to organize type A, B and C courses, qualification courses, for the occupation “Mountain Farmer” (SV authorization no. 000144/2009), and for “Tourist boarding house administrator” (SV authorization no. 000109/2008) as well as training courses, focusing on those organized on request.

The management of the institution was ensured by: Dr. Eng. Pogan Gheorghe - General Manager of ANZM; Dr. Eng. Dănuț Gițan - Director of CEFIDEC and Livia Popa, Head of Office, Financial, Accounting, Legal, Human Resources Management.

In August 2010, the National Agency for Mountain Areas was abolished, according to GEO 70/2010 regarding some measures for the reorganization of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, as well as some structures under its subordination. (Art. 10 (1) & (2)).

Out of the total of 33 employees of the institution, existing at that time, were taken over by examination / transfer at the General Management for Rural Development AM PNDR within the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development - MADR (Fig. 7) a number of 13 employees: 10 specialists in different fields of activity, with the professional degree of senior advisor, 2 specialists in the economic field (senior advisor and main advisor) and the administrator of the institution. They continued their activity in the building from Vatra Dornei, performing both activities specific to the mountain area and the National Rural Development Program 2007 - 2013, respectively 2014 - 2020.

The main activities carried out within the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development DGDR AM PNDR [5]:

- Evaluation of projects financed by Measure 141 within the National Rural Development Program - PNDR;
- Evaluation of funding projects for Local Action Groups (LAGs);
- Field verifications of the Projects accessed through Measure 141;
- Technical expertise / analysis / points of view for the Guides elaborated within PNDR;
- Technical expertise on the mountain area: answers to notifications / addresses / petitions;
- Participation as members in the Thematic Working Groups;
- Dissemination of information necessary for public information of potential beneficiaries - Axis 3;
- Elaboration of development strategies for the mountain area;
- Elaboration of the Socio-economic Analysis of the mountain area;
- Contributions to the elaboration of the National Rural Development Program 2014-2020;
- Specialized technical assistance.

Fig. 7 Logos of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and of National Rural Development Program (2007-2013, respectively, 2014-2020). Official logos used by the General Management for Rural Development MA PNDR

The management of the institution was ensured by: ec. Cornelia Harabagiu - general manager (2010 - 2012) and ec. Mihai Herciu - general manager (2012 - 2015).

After taking over the headquarters in Vatra Dornei and of the specialists by the Ministry of Agriculture, the European association for cooperation in the Euromontana mountain areas, through its president Andre Marcon, sent an official letter to the Romanian Government and the Minister of Agriculture regarding the error committed by abolishing ANZM and CEFIDEC [13]. The Romanian Mountain Forum Association, through its president, Prof. Dr. Radu Rey, addressed a memorandum to the competent forums (Romanian Presidency, Government, Ministry of Agriculture) for the re-establishment of the National Agency for Mountain Areas and the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians. The main arguments are the expertise of the 12 specialists with an experience between 14 and 19 years in the mountain area, but also the existing material base at Vatra Dornei [6], [15].

In 2014, by GD 1189/2014 was established the Mountain Area Agency - AZM (Fig. 8) according to Law no. 139/2014 on some measures for the reorganization of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, as well as some structures subordinated to it, with subsequent amendments [9]. Institution based in Vatra Dornei, Suceava County, in the same building where CEFIDEC or the DGDR AM PNDR service operated. And the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians has become a department within AZM. In addition to this direction, there was also the Office of Strategies, Policies and Programs for Sustainable Development of the Mountain Area [5].

From the total of 12 existing specialists at the headquarters in Vatra Dornei, employees of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development DGDR AM PNDR, a number of 3 specialists were taken over by the Mountain Area Agency, 1 specialist was taken over by the Suceava County Rural Development Department of MADR, and 8 were moved to the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development in Bucharest. The agency also hired 23 specialists in different fields through competition, the total number of employees being 26 people [5].

The global objective of the Mountain Area Agency was the development and protection of mountain areas in Romania, areas marked by specificity, ecologically fragile and economically and socially disadvantaged due to natural causes, areas that required specific management.

Fig. 8. Inauguration of the Mountain Area Agency (March 5, 2015)

From a strategic point of view, AZM was aiming to implement the National Strategic Guidelines for the sustainable development of the disadvantaged mountain area (2014-2020), approved by the Romanian Government through a Memorandum, in May 2014.

The Agency aimed to apply the Government's strategies and policies in the field of development and protection of mountain areas in Romania. AZM's mission aimed at sustainable development and increased attractiveness of the mountain area in Romania, by:

- highlighting the resources;
- stabilizing the mountain population;
- maintaining cultural identity;
- increasing the economic power at local level, in the conditions of maintaining the ecological balance and the protection of the natural environment.

The objectives pursued by ANZM:

- Increasing the economic competitiveness of the mountain area;
- Increasing the attractiveness of the disadvantaged mountain area and stabilizing the mountain population;
- Improving the quality of environmental factors and conserving biodiversity;
- Conservation and capitalization of cultural resources.

The Mountain Area Agency organized vocational training courses for farmers, beneficiaries of the following measures within the National Rural Development Program:

- Measure 10 Agri-environment and climate;
- Measure 11 Organic farming.

AZM contributed to the elaboration of the following normative acts [5]:

- Government Decision no. 506 of 20 July 2016 on establishing the institutional framework and measures for the implementation of Delegated Regulation (EU) no. 665/2014 of the Commission of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) no. 1,151 / 2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council regarding the conditions of use of the optional quality term "mountain product"

- Order no. 52 of March 3, 2017 on the approval of the Procedure for verifying the conformity of the data contained in the specifications in order to grant the right to use the optional quality term "mountain product" and to verify compliance with European and Chinese legislation by economic operators who have obtained the right to use that specific statement. Completed / amended by Order 321/2017, Order 31/2018, Order 49/2019, Order 328/2019 and Order 585/2020.

- Order of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development No. 97 of February 19, 2019 / Ministry of Regional Development and Public Administration No. 1.332 of March 14, 2019 regarding the approval of the classification criteria and the list of localities in the mountain area

- Law 197/2018 - Mountain Law

- Law 334/2018 - for the approval of the Program to encourage investments in the mountain area

- Law 296/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of milk collection and / or processing centers in the mountain area

- Law 330/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of centers for collection, washing and primary processing of wool and leather in the mountain area

- Law 331/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of small capacity units for slaughtering animals and / or meat processing in the mountain area

- Law 332/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of mountain sheepfolds

- Law 333/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of centers for the collection and primary processing of berries, mushrooms and/ or medicinal and aromatic plants from spontaneous flora and/ or culture in the mountain area.

The management of the institution was provided by: dr. Ec. Lazăr Latu - general manager, dr. Eng. Dănuț Gițan- director, director of the Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians and dr. Eng. Dănuț Ungureanu - head of office, Office of Strategies, Policies and Programs for Sustainable Development.

In 2018, the National Mountain Area Agency is organized, according to GD 1036/2018 for the organization and operation of the National Mountain Area Agency through reorganizing the Mountain Area Agency, as well as for establishing measures on regional centers and mountain development offices. (CEFIDEC remains as a directorate within ANZM, and the Bureau of Policies and Programs for Sustainable Development of the Mountain Area is transformed into a direction, being called the Directorate of Strategies, Policies and Programs for the Development of the Mountain Area).

The National Agency for Mountain Areas (ANZM), was established in accordance with the provisions of the Mountain Law no. 197/2018 and H.G. NO. 1036/2018 for the reorganization and functioning of the National Agency of the Mountain Area through

reorganizing the Agency of the Mountain Area, as well as for the establishment of some measures regarding the regional centers and the mountain development offices [10]. The Agency has its headquarters in the same location - Vatra Dornei municipality, Runc street no. 26, Suceava county and is directly subordinated to the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development.

The main role of the National Agency for Mountain Areas is to develop and implement strategies and policies for the development and protection of mountain areas in Romania, areas marked by specificity, ecologically fragile and economically and socially disadvantaged due to natural causes, which require a specific approach, and implementation of measures within the National Rural Development Program 2014-2020, financially supported by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the state budget.

Fig. 9. Logos of the Mountain Area Agency (2014 - 2018) and National Agency of Mountain Area 2018 - 2020 (present)

Within ANZM, were created territorial structures: 7 Regional Mountain Development Centers and 32 Mountain Development Offices. For a better cooperation with the ministry and in order to exist a decision factor of the Agency at MADR, the director of DSPPDZM was delegated to Bucharest to work in the Ministry of Agriculture [5].

Since the establishment of ANZM, professional training courses have been organized for farmers, beneficiaries of the following measures within PNDR:

- Measure 10 Agri-environment and climate
- Measure 11 Organic farming
- Sub-measure 6.1 Installation of young farmers
- Sub-measure 6.3 Support for the development of small farms

AMZM contributed to the elaboration of the following normative acts:

- Government Decision no. 332/2019 on establishing the composition, attributions and responsibilities of the massif committee and of the National Mountain Council.
- Order 760 / R / 2019 regarding the approval of the regional mountain development centers, of the mountain development offices, of the place of activity as well as of the counties and the assigned territorial administrative units.
- Order 347/2019 for the amendment of Annex no. 2 at the Order of the Minister of Agriculture and Rural Development no. 760 / R / 2019 regarding the approval of the regional mountain development centers, of the mountain development offices, of the place of activity as well as of the counties and the assigned territorial administrative units.

At this date, the normative acts are on the institution's website, in public debate:

- Emergency ordinance for the amendment and completion of Law no. 333/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of centers for the collection and primary processing of berries, mushrooms and / or medicinal and aromatic plants from spontaneous flora and / or culture in the mountain area

- Emergency ordinance for the amendment of Law no. 332/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of mountain sheepfolds

- Emergency ordinance for the amendment of Law no. 296/2018 on the approval of the Investment Program for the establishment of milk collection and / or processing centers in the mountain area.

The Agency for the Financing of Rural Investments (AFIR) announces the launch between 13 July and 31 December 2020 of the first session of 2020 for the submission of Financing Applications for sub-measure 4.2 "Support for investments in processing / marketing of agricultural products - investment component in small capacity slaughterhouses in the mountain area" from the National Rural Development Program 2014 - 2020 (PNDR 2020).

During 2020, ANZM developed a Program for the development of mountain agrotourism as well as the Plan for Sustainable Development of the Mountain Area.

Also during this period, specialists from the institution participate in the working groups organized by the Ministry of Agriculture (DGDR AM PNDR) for the elaboration of the National Strategic Plan 2021 - 2027.

The management of the institution is ensured by: dr. Ec. Lazăr Latu - general manager, dr. Eng. Dănuț Gîțan- director, directorate of Training and Innovation Center for Development in the Carpathians and ec. Veronica Țăran Baciu - Directorate of Strategies, Policies and Development Programs of the Mountain Area.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the creation of the Romanian Mountain Area Commission in 1990, in order to respond to the needs of the mountain area, developing international experiences and national initiatives, the Romanian Ministry of Agriculture created in 1994, at the initiative of Prof. Dr. Radu Rey - secretary of state within the ministry, a training center for mountain specifics, to come to the aid of specialists but also of farmers in the mountain area. Under the direct coordination of the National Agency for Mountain Areas, and then the Directorate-General for Rural Development, over the years have been held both training courses and qualification courses for mountain specifics. Another component of the institution's activity was innovation, provided mainly by the construction design workshop.

Over the years, due to the periodic political changes, the institution from Vatra Dornei has undergone several transformations, reorganizations, and even abolitions. Until 2009, when it was taken over by the National Agency for Mountain Areas, it had a winding, but somewhat balanced course. The abolition of ANZM in Alba Iulia in 2010 meant an injustice both for the mountain area and for the existing staff, trained and practiced over a long period of time.

MADR tried to "save" a small number of specialists and to capitalize their experience, between 2010 and 2015, year after which the nucleus from Vatra Dornei was crushed.

By re-establishing the Mountain Area Agency in 2014, and then the National Mountain Area Agency in 2019, in the same location - in Vatra Dornei, a new challenge is born. Here are hired and trained new specialists who, in a relatively short time, have managed to contribute to mountain development, developing draft regulations, growth plans, providing specialized advice or participating in the professional training of farmers. The law of the

mountain is a good example for the realization of the team of specialists, and the mention of optional quality "mountain product" is a reality for mountain agricultural producers

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